

Book Review

Crosslinguistic Influence and Second Language Learning

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Language learning is forming the language knowledge with the exposure of language. Language knowledge is continuous, and experience-driven. So practice is necessary to develop this new knowledge in L2 learning. Crosslinguistic influence refers to the effect of a language on another (Alonso,2019). The influence is dynamic, and mutual. Because L2 learning requires the creation of the new knowledge and selection mechanism between L1 and L2.

Experience can either facilitate L2 learning process or slow down it depending on the similarities and differences in L1 and L2.

The book starts with an introduction on a comprehensive overview of crosslinguistic influence in adult second language learning. The introduction presents the main purposes of the book and the outline of five chapters in the book. The aim of the book is to explore how adults build knowledge of an additional language, * whether learning a new language lead to broader changes in a speaker's existing system or not, * whether connections among different languages emerge and change over time or not and * whether instruction can help L2 learners overcome some negative effects of crosslinguistic influence or not. With this aim, the book reviews theories of language learning, empirical studies of L2 learning on crosslinguistic influence, instructional studies on negative effects of crosslinguistic influence. Firstly, some key concepts such as language, learning a second language, prior knowledge, experience, transfer, cross-language relationships, directions of crosslinguistic influence, explicit instruction and crosslinguistic influence are described briefly to make readers understand the content [to help to make readers understand better].

Chapter 2 discusses four theoretical models of L2 learning that explain how speakers use and learn another language. These models are The Unified Competition Model by MacWhinney, the Associate-Cognitive CREED by Ellis, Processing Determinism by O'Grady, and the Inhibitory Control Model [by Green. The *UCM model is based on some premises such as cues, validity, availability, reliability, competition, transfer, entrenchment, and decoupling. According to this model, different cues in L1, and L2 or same cues with different cue strengths create learning difficulties by cause of entrenchment and transfer from L1. The major principles of the Associative-Cognitive CREED are that language learning is rational, exemplar-based, emergent, and dialectic. According to this model, transfer of L1 knowledge about form-meaning mapping and learned processing behaviour plays an important role in learning difficulties. In other words the same cues with different meanings in L1, and L2 or blocked new cues during real-time processing cause learning difficulty. Processing Determinism Model explains how L2 speakers learn to produce and process language. It is based on two premises such as amelioration and transfer calculus. According to this model, L2 learning is perceived with the help of processing amelioration, that is, improving performance by creating dominant routines if they are not costly to complete. The Inhibitory Control Model explains how speakers manage the languages. According to this model, language representations are connected with language tags and inhibitory control suppress tags of undesired language as the representations of both L1, and L2 are activated together. At the end of the chapter, the similarities and differences of the models are examined.

In **Chapter 3**, empirical L2 researches about crosslinguistic influence in morphosyntax, vocabulary, and phonology are discussed. Moreover, the chapter tries to find answer what is known about crosslinguistic effects in L2 development and whether the instruction supports L2 learning. According to results of the research on morphosyntax, L2 learning influences a speaker's L1 system by converging of L1 and L2 knowledge, changing the representations, and the way where they are accessed. According to results of the research on vocabulary, L2 learning influences the L1 storage, and access as it causes to the re-organization of L1 representations, and the development of new access to L1 knowledge. According to results of the research on phonology, L1 phonology is important for L2 speech learning as the different or absent L1 sounds are too difficult to learn.

Chapter 4 focuses on the findings of L2 research, and the theories of L2 used in second language learning. So this chapter emphasizes on how explicit instruction] and explicit knowledge that focus on crosslinguistic influence facilitates learning. According to the studies conducted on the effectiveness of the explicit instruction, awareness of differences and similarities in L1 and L2 leads to the improvement of L2 ability.

Chapter 5 reviews the organization and restructuring of knowledge, experience, cross-language relationships, instruction, and reflections on crosslinguistic influence. Furthermore, the storage of the language knowledge, the influence of the experience on language processing, and use, the cognition forming language use, support of the instruction on L2 learning are emphasized. The crosslinguistic influence in L2 learning, especially transfer as a core

learning process, is revised to theorize in SLA field. The new directions in crosslinguistic influence, the whole language system, a focus on longitudinal accounts of L2 learning, aspects of the general cognition are also emphasized in this chapter.

The book suggests reading sources for researchers as well. It also includes summary of the suggested books. These suggestions can be a good source for those who want to learn more about crosslinguistic influence. Moreover, the book can be regarded as a great resource for those who want to describe the ways adults learn other languages, and how the speakers' experience affect the processing and use of the other languages.

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